

Co-thinking and Creation for STEAM

diversity-gap reduction

2020-1-ES01-KA201-082601

Co-funded by the
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of the European Union

Teacher Training

IDEATE – CONTEXTUALIZE - REQUIREMENTS

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April 19th, 2021

Online documentation

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5778978>

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1.- IDEATING THE STEAM-LAB

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STEAM-Lab Action Plan - PHASE 2: IDEATE

School:

Person:

Date:

2. IDEATE

2.1. Proposal of the STEAM-Lab **space distribution and tools**.

2.1.1. Attach the list of **tools** planned for 1, 2, 5 years.

You can find the tool's map at https://coggle.it/diagram/X-Cy2_YZrx-l8zDJ/t/technology-in-a-steam-lab-star

For 1 year (short term):

For 2 years (medium term):

For 5 years (long term):

2.1.2. Draw the contour of the STEAM-Lab space of your school in MIRO and make a general **distribution** by zones of use and tools.

You can find an example at https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_I0BhHOU=

2.2. Proposal of the STEAM-Lab **organization and management**.

2.2.1. Write names and associated responsibilities/roles of the **steering committee**: teachers, students, families, other. Associated responsibilities.

2.2.2. Make a first draft of the **space management regulations**: schedules, rules of conduct, and security.

2.2.3. Write a first draft of **measurable goals** for 1, 2, 5 years for the STEAM-Lab space.

For 1 year (short term):

For 2 years (medium term):

For 5 years (long term):

2.2.4. Write a draft of continuous improvement or **sustainability** plan for the STEAM-Lab.
(For example, it can include indicators of its use, teacher training plan, and resources to make it sustainable over time, dissemination plan, etc.)

2.2.5. Will there be sponsors, service or membership fees...?

2.2.6. How will you overcome the risks stated in the Action Plan - CONTEXTUALIZE 1.3?

(Write down a brief mitigation plan for the risks stated in the Action Plan - CONTEXTUALIZE 1.3)

2.3. **Pedagogical** proposal in the STEAM-Lab.

2.3.1. Think and write schematically. What kind of **projects, didactic units, activities or initiatives** will be developed in the STEAM-Lab, and their link with the curriculum? What is the flagship or star project that you want to promote or with which will you start? Will it be interdisciplinary? Will it promote creativity? Will it cover a social and inclusive approach, and the diversity challenges listed above?

2.3.2. Think and write. What **teaching/learning methodology** will be developed in the STEAM-Lab? Underline the option or options that best suit you.

Active Learning
Project based Learning
Personalization of learning and Inclusive environment
Service-learning
Collaborative learning
Design Thinking methodologies
Inquiry Based Learning
Tinkering
Others (indicate which ones)

2.4. Proposal of the **ecosystem** of the STEAM-Lab.

2.4.1. Think about how the STEAM-Lab will **interconnect** with the community (families, local industry, educational platforms, other STEAM-Labs, etc.).

Students and the educational community are involved in the co-creation of the space and related projects? The school has strong connections with families, local industry, other educational platforms? Consider also creating facebook, twitter or blog page for your users.

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2.- CONTEXTUALIZING THE STEAM-LAB

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Action Plan STEAM-Lab - PHASE 1: CONTEXTUALIZE

School:

Name of the person who fills the document:

Date:

1. CONTEXTUALIZE

1.1. What is the **mission** of developing a STEAM-Lab at your school?

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1.2. Reflect on the context in your school and in the educational environment. Broadly speaking, what groups of **users** do you envisage in the STEAM-Lab and what related **needs** do you want to cover with the STEAM-Lab?

USERS	NEEDS

1.3. Reflect on possible **Gains** and **Risks** of the creation of the STEAM-Lab.

GAINS	RISKS

1.4. What **diversity** and inclusion challenges do you want to work on within the STEAM-Lab?
Underline the option or options that best suit in your school.

Diversity (gender gap)
Diversity (economics - social classes, etc.)
Diversity (immigration - language, etc.)
Diversity (disabilities - ADHD, etc.)

1.5. Current resources that are available: Reflect on the resources that you currently have to set up a STEAM-Lab at school: Do you have a space? Are there people interested in your school that could form a steering committee? Are there currently technological tools that you plan to include in the STEAM-Lab? Do you have the possibility of acquiring equipment for the STEAM-Lab?

You can copy the current tools indicated in the Questionnaire_StartingPoint_STEAM-Lab at <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1uwdvE-Gb0sFB0yxGoYX3hPMKYAXPctZg/view?usp=sharing>

Space (attach current photos of the space):

Responsible and Steering Committee:

Current tools:

Do you have possibilities of acquiring new equipment for the STEAM-Lab ?:

1.6. Get inspired: Copy below 3 images that could inspire you for the STEAM-Lab at your school. We invite you to search for them through Pinterest, Google Image search, FreePik; using "STEAM-Lab", "FabLab", "Maker Space" as the search term.

A large, empty rectangular box with a black border, intended for pasting three images that inspire the user for their STEAM-Lab.

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3.- REQUIREMENTS of STEAM-LAB (check-list)

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Minimum Requirements STEAM-Lab Checklist

Underline YES or NO

School: _____

School Infrastructure

- Separate space YES/NO
- Integrates students, promotes inclusion YES/NO
- Access to technology and equipment YES/NO

Curricula Implementation

- Emphasis on STEM subjects (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) YES/NO
- Interdisciplinary learning YES/NO
- Emphasis on creativity YES/NO
- Addresses diversity gap YES/NO

Pedagogical Approach

- Active learning YES/NO
- Project based learning YES/NO
- Personalisation of learning and Inclusive environment YES/NO
- Service-learning YES/NO
- Collaborative learning YES/NO
- Inquiry Based learning YES/NO
- Design Thinking methodologies YES/NO
- Tinkering

Results

- Interdisciplinary and inclusive didactic units, projects, challenges YES/NO
- Measure and share impact.- Document and share learning processes. YES/NO

School Culture

- School leadership YES/NO
- High level of cooperation among staff YES/NO
- Inclusive culture YES/NO
- Students and the educational community are involved in the co-creation of the space and related projects. YES/NO
- The school has strong connections with families, local industry, other educational platforms. YES/NO